

Peculiarities of cooperation between Turkey and the European Union in modern international relations

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Abstract: Trade relations between Turkey and the European Union are a complex and multifaceted topic. Mutual economic interests, political differences and historical ties determine the dynamics of trade relations between the two countries. This article attempts to comprehensively study the internal political struggle in Turkey, bilateral trade relations, migration issues, the country's accession to the European Union, the positions of pro-Western politicians and their opposition to the West. The results of the study allow us to reflect on the socio-political processes in Turkey in connection with the choice of the pro-European path. In addition, the strategy of energy exchange between Turkey and the European Union is explained in detail.

Keywords: Trade and economic relations, cooperation, integration, Customs Union, trade barriers, political situation, political differences.

Особенности сотрудничества Турции и Евросоюза в современных международных отношениях

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Аннотация: Торговые отношения между Турцией и Европейским Союзом – сложная и многогранная тема. Взаимные экономические интересы, политические разногласия и исторические связи определяют динамику торговых отношений между этими двумя странами. В данной статье предпринята попытка комплексно изучить внутривнутриполитическую борьбу в Турции, двусторонние торговые отношения, миграционные проблемы, вступление страны в Евросоюз, позиции прозападных политиков и их противостояние Западу. Результаты исследования позволяют задуматься о общественно-политических процессах в Турции в связи с выбором проевропейского пути. Кроме того, подробно объясняется стратегия обмена энергоресурсами между Турцией и Европейским Союзом.

Ключевые слова: Торгово-экономические отношения, сотрудничество, интеграция, Таможенный союз, торговые барьеры, политическая обстановка, политические разногласия.

The Republic of Turkey has a large territory, a large population, a powerful economy and armed forces, scientific and social potential and occupies an excellent position among the countries of Europe and Asia. The influence of this country, especially on the European continent, is significant (for example, Germany, Austria, etc.). The geographical position of the country and the level of economic, cultural and historical ties in its region demonstrate Turkey's potential to exert great influence in Europe and Asia. The country's non-admission to the European Union for a number of objective and subjective reasons does not affect the foreign or domestic policy of this country at all. The political position and sphere of economic influence of the Republic of Turkey in the Black Sea region, the Middle East, the Balkan Peninsula, the Mediterranean region and Central Asia are very strong. In our opinion, European countries consider Turkey, firstly, as the most powerful country in the region, secondly, as a transit country for the transportation of energy resources, thirdly, as a country that holds back migrants who want to come to Europe, and fourthly, as a country that holds back migrants who want to come to Europe. , he is against some Arab countries being recognized as masters of the economy. The Republic of Turkey is a country that actively participates in noteworthy peacekeeping operations within the UN, OSCE and NATO, and also acts as a region where products made in Europe can be sold. If we look at history, after the death of Mustafa Kemal Atatürk, the foreign policy of the Turkish Republic was characterized by volatility, instability and slowness. (10.57-58p)

As a result of the state policy implemented in the 60s and 90s of the twentieth century, it is clear that relations with European countries were based on the deterioration of relations with neighboring countries. Turkey had serious territorial, economic and political disputes with all its immediate neighbors. In addition, it can be noted that the country's foreign policy problems are increasing every year. One of the most prominent politicians of Turkey, former Prime Minister Mahmud Davutoglu stated that in order to solve the above-mentioned problematic situations and prevent new dangerous situations that may arise in the course of foreign policy, Turkey adopted the "Strategic Development Concept". " " and consistently implements it in practice, the essence of this concept is to make completely new decisions in Turkey's foreign policy on some interstate issues, shift the main focus from the West to the East, update elements of foreign policy, This is manifested in the implementation of such principles as the use of new forms of secrecy (with the support of the Turkish diaspora living abroad). It is also worth noting that the main focus of the concept is the mediation of the Turkish Republic in solving international problems that have not been resolved for many years (for

example, with close neighbors). Such problems include conflicts in Nagorno-Karabakh, Cyprus, Iraq, Syria, Israel and Palestine.

Currently, the foreign policy of the Republic of Turkey is distinguished by the fact that it is carried out separately in relation to Western and Eastern countries. Turkey, based on its geostrategic interests, the United States, Europe (mainly Germany, France and Italy). Russia and China try to maintain equal distances in international relations. Turkey's relations with Russia are characterized by instability and instability. There have been more wars between Turkey and Russia than between any other country, and for centuries, these two countries have been strategic enemies.(1.12p)

One of the main features of Turkey's foreign policy is that the country carries out international cooperation based on pragmatism and actively resolves international issues with close neighbors and closest allies.

Turkey's foreign policy also depends on the reputation of the country's leadership in the international arena. Since Recep Tayyip Erdogan has great positions in the countries of the East and West, this situation has a great impact on interstate relations. As an example, we can see cases where Turkey pays great attention to trade with Russia, Uzbekistan, France and Germany. In our opinion, the country's interstate relations with the United States, Russia and Iran occupy a leading place in Turkey's foreign policy. At present, relations between the Turkish Republic and Western countries are becoming increasingly cold. It is safe to say that Western countries (particularly the United States) have pursued a specific policy in solving the Kurdish problem and have provided military support to Kurdish armed groups, which has become one of the main factors that have led to the deterioration of Turkey's relations with Western countries. This situation has had a positive effect on Turkey's close relations with Russia and Iran.

Another factor is that Turkey's relations with organizations such as the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), Brazil, South Africa, Russia, India and China (BRICS) have become active, which is a sign of Ankara's active foreign policy.

Recep Tayyip Erdogan's efforts to create a great, stable and self-sufficient society, first of all, have caused Turkey to cool towards its traditional allies (Turkey, being a member of NATO, had very close relations with Europe and the United States). lays the foundation for strengthening relations with new allies.

In our opinion, the weakening of Turkey's relations with Western countries is connected with the desire of Turkish business circles (they have a great influence on the economic life of the country) to open new allies and new markets for the transfer of their material goods. For example, most Turkish businessmen are in favor of strengthening relations with Russia, Iran, Pakistan, Azerbaijan, Uzbekistan

and other Eastern countries and call for a decrease in the level of trade and political relations in the Western direction.

Now let's turn to the main situations that determine Turkey's foreign policy towards Western countries:

First of all, if we look at the recent history of Turkey, we will see that the country has close ties with Western countries, membership in various associations and organizations in Europe, and we can also observe trade with Western countries. Over the past 15 years, the foreign policy of the Turkish Republic has been completely oriented, and it can be clearly seen that it has undergone serious transformation processes. Secondly, if earlier Turkey experienced economic and political crises, absolute power of the military, close communication only with Western countries and instability in foreign policy, now we are witnessing a well-thought-out, step-by-step foreign policy. Thirdly, the very advantageous geostrategic location of the Turkish Republic (at the junction of the West and the East) with common borders with Greece and Bulgaria in the West, Georgia, Armenia, Iran, Iraq, Syria in the East and Romania, Ukraine, and Russia at sea is the reason for Turkey's current foreign policy. Fourth, the fact that Turkey's policy is currently carried out on the basis of the principle of long-term stable relations with close neighbors. (9.66p)

Fifth, Turkey's foreign policy is carried out on the basis of Atatürk, the founder of the country, on the basis of the principle of "peace in the country, peace in the world."

Sixth, it should be emphasized that in the modern period, Turkey's foreign policy is based on two main principles: "problem-free establishment of relations with neighbors" and "creation of a belt of stability and security around Turkey."

Seventh, it should be emphasized that Turkey's foreign policy, based on the above principles, does not pay much attention to the Western direction.

Eighth, the fact that Turkey's foreign policy has deep conceptual foundations.

Ninth, the fact that the Republic of Turkey, unlike Western countries, deeply thinks about maintaining the place and position of the United Nations (UN) as the most important international organization in the world.

Tenth, Turkey, as a NATO member, insists on the need to jointly form a concept of European security with Russia, to support new international formats, and not the top 7, but the top 20.

Eleventh, despite the fact that the Republic of Turkey is a NATO member, it advocates independent and free relations with other countries.

Twelfth, Turkey's main goal is to bring the republic into the top ten most developed countries and achieve the status of a regional leader in the technological

direction, taking into account the celebration of the country's 100th anniversary in 2023.

Thirteenth, Turkey's foreign policy is influenced by the fact that international oil and gas pipelines pass through the country, it has a large merchant fleet (about 300 large ships), as well as a fleet of trucks (about 50,000) designed to transport large loads, skillfully using it. Fourteenth, the Turkish government and state-owned humanitarian organizations (such as TIKA, etc.) have close ties with the population of Turkish nationality living in European countries, and their influence is used and exploited in the interests of the Turkish state. Fifth, in our opinion, Turkish leaders do not consider their country's membership in NATO and close ties with Europe and the United States as the only factors that ensure the security of their country's territory. At present, a phenomenon that has not yet been observed on the geopolitical map of the world is the fact that Turkey is moving away from traditional allies and closer to its neighbors and pursuing a policy that prioritizes trade. In addition, the country is rapidly approaching the SCO and BRICS organizations. (3.78-79p)

If we pay attention to the literature published in Turkey, we will be sure of the correctness of the above ideas. For example, Turks live more often in Russia, Azerbaijan and Uzbekistan than in the USA, Great Britain, France and Germany. They emphasize the need to develop relations with Iran, Kazakhstan, China and other Eastern countries. At the same time, we are talking not only about countries where Islam dominates, but also about other countries.

In our opinion, if Western countries take into account the above features of Turkey, fully understand the concept of foreign policy, and then enter into interstate relations with this country, they will not exclude Turkey from the list of countries with their own interests.

If we pay attention to the existing foreign and domestic scientific research, we can point out another factor that has led to the weakening of Turkey's political and other relations in the direction of Europe and the United States. This is also the fact that the youth of Turkey has absorbed the values (including mass culture) of Western countries, but they still respect the Islamic religion and the values of the Islamic religion and do not forget the traditions that have formed over the course of a century. An example of this is the fact that currently about 6 million people of Turkish nationality live in European countries, where they respect the traditions left by their ancestors. It is clear to everyone that they have a significant influence on the majority of young people living in Turkey.

Far-sighted European politicians, including EU President D. Tusk, European Commission President J.C. Juncker and others, are interested in reviving the cold relations with Turkey and intensifying relations in various areas. In addition,

former US President D. Trump is also a supporter of establishing close relations with Turkey. Western leaders should also understand that Turkish President Recep Tayyip Erdogan is a politician who resolutely defends the national interests of his country and, in a word, puts mutual interests first. Without this, relations between the West and Turkey would remain in decline. On the other hand, given that Turkey is currently the leader in Europe in the exchange of gas and oil, the EU's desire to strengthen cooperation with Turkey is one of the Union's strategies. We can see the work carried out in this direction on the official websites of the Turkish and EU Foreign Ministries. Energy is one of the most important topics in relations between Turkey and the European Union. As a sign of the great importance attached to regional energy cooperation, with its indispensable position in ensuring European energy security, Turkey joined the Energy Community with observer status in 2006. As part of Turkey's EU membership negotiations, the "energy sector" review process was completed in 2007. Turkey wants to open the energy section of the negotiations as soon as possible. Long-term contract between TEİAŞ and ENTSO-E

On 15 April 2015, the relevant boards of the Turkish Electricity Transmission Company ("TEİAŞ") and the European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity (ENTSO-E) signed a long-term agreement ensuring the physical integration of the European electricity market. . Turkish electricity market, ensuring the seamless connection of the Turkish electricity systems to the electricity system of the European continents. Thus, advanced integration between the Turkish electricity system and electricity market as well as the internal European electricity market was realized. (8.90p)

Key statistics on the Turkish energy sector and monthly sector reports from TÜİK (Energy Market Regulatory Authority) and EPDK (Turkish Statistical Institute) can be found at the following links.

Turkey has achieved the fastest growth in energy demand among the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) countries over the past 20 years. During this period, Türkiye ranks second after China in terms of growth in demand for electricity and natural gas in the world.

Turkey, which has about 60 percent of the world's proven oil and natural gas reserves, has become one of the largest natural gas and electricity markets in its region.

On the other hand, Turkey relies on imports for 74 percent of its energy needs. The diverse structure of Turkey's energy strategy and its dependence on energy imports bring international relations in this area to the forefront.

One of the main goals of Turkey's energy strategy is to diversify routes and resources to strengthen energy security. Turkey also aims to contribute to regional

and global energy security and become a regional energy trading hub. The main elements that make up the international dimension of Turkey's energy strategy are:

1. To ensure diversification of oil and natural gas supply routes and resources in light of growing demand and dependence on imports;
2. To contribute to regional and global energy security,
3. To be a regional energy trading hub;
4. Consideration of social and environmental impacts in the context of sustainable development at each stage of the energy chain,
5. Increasing the share of local and renewable energy in electricity production,
6. Inclusion of nuclear energy in the energy mix. Turkey continues its efforts to increase the share of renewable energy in the national energy mix and include nuclear energy in the energy mix in order to reduce dependence on energy imports, maximize the use of local resources and combat climate change. (11.124p)

Renewable Energy

Turkey attaches great importance to the development of renewable energy. According to the National Energy Policy adopted in 2017, increasing the use of local and renewable energy sources is one of the top priorities. In addition, Turkey ranks 5th in Europe and 12th in the world in terms of installed renewable energy capacity. The share of renewable energy in Turkey's installed capacity will reach 54% by the end of 2022.

Turkey is currently one of the most important trading partners of the EU. In 2023, the trade volume between Turkey and the EU will reach €170 billion. The EU is Turkey's largest export market and more than 40% of Turkey's total exports come from imports of goods and food products. Turkey exports cars, clothing, textiles, fruits and vegetables, and metal products to the EU. Trade relations between Turkey and the EU have a number of problems:

- Political differences: There are factors that strain relations, such as delays in Turkey's EU membership process, disputes over human rights and democracy, and the Cyprus issue.

- Turkey's economic reforms: Turkey's efforts to liberalize its economy and move toward a market economy could increase its trade with the EU.- European Union Policy: EU trade policy with Turkey depends on various factors.

Trade relations between Turkey and the EU are complex and dynamic. Despite political differences and other factors, the volume of trade between the two sides is increasing every year. In the future, depending on the impact of economic and political conditions, different prospects are expected.

REFERENCES

1. Alekperov. R. The role of style in the domestic and foreign policy of Turkey after World War II Author's abstr... candidate of political science-M.2007-P.12-14
2. Aziz al-Azmeh. Islam and modernity. - M. 2009.P.17
3. Shamsutdinov A. M. National liberation war in Turkey 1918-1923
4. Nakisbaev D.V. USA - ES - Turkey. Modern Europe / Diplomatic Academy of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Russia [ed. T.A. Zakaurtseva], M.: Vostok-Zapad, 2008.
5. Turkey in Europe. Second Report of the Independent Commission on Turkey. September 2009.
6. Shlykov V.I. Evolution of the Party System in Turkey during the Turkish Republic (1983-2007) // Turkey in the Past. M., 2008.
7. Kudryashova Yu.S. Turkey and the European Union: History, Problems and Prospects. M., 2010.
8. Redmond John, "Turkey and the European Union: Problematic Europe or European Problems?" International Affairs, Vol. 83, No. 2 (2007).
9. Karpat K. Turkey's Foreign Policy: Some Introductory Remarks. Istanbul, 2003.
10. Kornilov A.A. Center for Strategic Studies of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Turkey: Features of Operation and Expertise Staff // Current Issues in the Study of Modern Turkey: Proceedings of the International Scientific Conference. N. Novgorod: ISI NNSU, 2007.
11. Redmond John, "Turkey and the European Union: Problematic Europe or European Problems?" International Affairs, Vol. 83, No. 2 (2007).